

Biochemical Fuel Cells

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The need for tapping sources of energy other than the conventional ones necessitates the development of biochemical fuel cells in which a large variety of biomass can be used as fuels. The present status of biochemical fuel cells is reviewed. The main drawback of such fuel cell is the slow transfer of electrons from the substrate to the electrodes. Both experimental and theoretical studies have been started to understand the basic processes underlying the electron transfer in such systems. Preliminary results of such studies are very encouraging and further work in the area is in progress.

OUR energy demands are increasing and in view of the sky-rocketing price of petroleum products and the depletion of natural resources, it is becoming increasingly clear that sources of energy other than the conventional ones have to be tapped to meet the situation. The awareness of this situation and the possibilities of finding new sources of energy in the context of our own country have been highlighted recently¹.

The main conventional sources of energy today are fossil fuels, hydroelectricity and nuclear energy. Each of these has its own limitations and associated hazards. The devices using fossil fuels like coal, gasoline, diesel etc. generally operate through a heat cycle (Carnot cycle). The fuel is oxidised (burnt) and the thermal energy produced is utilized either to drive mechanical engines or is converted into electrical energy. The efficiencies of such devices are, however, limited by Carnot cycle and one obtains efficiency upto about 20%. To increase the efficiency of these systems, one has to go to higher operating temperatures which is again restricted by technological difficulties. It is, therefore, logical to look for devices which can directly convert chemical energy into electrical energy. This is, basically, accomplished in a fuel cell and the efficiency in fuel cell can be as high as 50%.

A fuel cell (FC) is an electrochemical device in which part of the energy derived from chemical reaction maintained by a continuous supply of chemical reactants is converted into electrical energy. In a biochemical fuel cell (BFC) the oxidation (burning) of bioorganic materials (fuels) is catalysed by specific enzymes. The electrochemical reactions usually take place with air as oxidant at the cathode while the enzymes catalyse the oxidation of bioorganic material at the anode. In general, one uses hydrogen or hydrogen rich fuels (SH₂) such as methane, methanol, ethanol, carbohydrates, etc. The energy producing reaction is the oxidation of hydrogen by oxygen

Such that the net reaction is

Each cell based on above reaction can produce few hundred watts of d.c. power. In a fuel cell power plant, several such cells can be stacked together.

Historically, the concept of biochemical fuel cell is not new. As far back as in 1911, Potter² observed that "disintegration of organic compounds is accompanied by the liberation of electrical energy". He constructed the first biochemical fuel cell and obtained voltages upto 0.35 volts from yeast-glucose systems. Cohen³ in 1931 did more precise work on generation of electrical energy from various cultures and sterile media. There was then a period of relatively low activity until early 1960's when the interest in biochemical fuel cells revived⁴⁻⁶. This activity was also initiated by several governmental and non-governmental agencies in U.S. like NASA, Magna Corpn., GEC, Ford Motors, Marquardt Corpn., Electron Molecule Research Inc., General Scientific Corpn., etc. but most of the outcome has remained classified for obvious reasons.

Design of biochemical fuel cells :

Fuel cells are different from batteries. This is due to the fact that fuel cells can supply power intermittently (reactants are fed and products removed continuously) and that the electrodes are not consumed. Most of the inorganic fuel cells use either highly alkaline (30-80% KOH) or highly acidic electrolyte media⁷, oxidation of hydrocarbon, methanol, ammonia or hydrogen as fuels and relatively expensive metallic electrodes to stand highly corrosive conditions. One has also to use high temperature and pressure because the fuels have a high activation energy and do not oxidize under ambient conditions. It is here that the use of specific enzymes (or bacteria) helps by lowering the barrier to chemical reactions and thus making the electrochemical reactions feasible under milder conditions. It has been estimated that for a direct electron transfer process, a current of the order of 10¹⁷ amp (at 1 volt) can be delivered by using 1 kg of enzyme⁸. For all practical purposes even a

millionth of the above current (10^{11} amp for 1 kg of pure enzyme) will be of valuable commercial application.

In the direct biochemical fuel cell, the oxidation of raw fuels such as starch, carbohydrate or protein is achieved with the help of bacteria via a stepwise transfer of protons involving several classes of enzymes and coenzymes (such as NAD), flavoprotein, cytochromes and coenzymes Q provided by the bacteria. The combustion rate in such cells is low since the reactions have to be carried out in a narrow range of pH and temperature.

The indirect biochemical cell works in two steps. The first step involves the conversion of raw fuel into simpler biochemical end products such as H_2 , CH_4 , NH_3 , CH_3OH , etc. with the help of suitable bacteria. The secondary fuel, thus generated, is transferred to a second compartment where the electrical power is generated in one step enzymatic oxidation of such products. While such systems are quite convenient and easier to optimize, there is an additional engineering problem which is the transfer of secondary fuel to the fuel cell compartment. Both types of biochemical fuel cells have been reported in the literature^{4-6,9-12}.

Many organic waste materials or natural sources can be used as fuel in biochemical fuel cells. Sisler⁴ reported a biochemical fuel cell which worked on undiluted sea water (which contains plant-carbohydrates synthesized by marine algae) through sulphate reducing bacteria, *Desulfovibrio desulfuricans* and obtained approx 0.5 volt with a current output of 1 milliamp. Colichman⁶ extended Sisler's study to a much broader application by utilizing various bio-fuels and obtained a better power level with fresh mushrooms serving as fuel by the catabolic action of *Desulfovibrio desulfuricans*. Many other biochemical fuel cells have been reported and some of these are :

- (i) hydrocarbon (natural gas) as fuel and hydrocarbon oxidizing bacteria as catalyst^{13,14},
- (ii) urea (urine) as fuel and urease (*Bacillus pasterii*) as catalyst⁶,
- (iii) glucose as fuel and glucose oxidase as catalyst¹¹,
- (iv) organic materials and hydrogenase to produce H_2 gas for use in the indirect fuel cells¹⁵.

Design difficulties :

There are several difficulties in designing biochemical fuel cells which provide challenges to technologists as well as to basic scientists. These systems have intrinsically low voltages (a typical redox system has voltage $\sim IV$) and hence they have to operate at high current densities to be of any practical use. The following problems arise in operating the systems at high current densities :

- (i) The transfer of electrons from the enzyme-fuel system to electrode is rather slow. At present there is no obvious solution to this problem although several groups are interested in electron transfer from biological macromolecules to conductors,

- (ii) The electrolyte should have a low electrical resistance and the extreme pH conditions or salt concentrations which are needed to increase the electrical conductance are injurious to the bacterial system. This problem can be overcome by the use of indirect cell system,
- (iii) The electrodes have to be designed from expensive materials and they have relatively short life due to corrosion and bacterial contamination. This problem again can be avoided by the use of indirect fuel cell operating on pure enzyme systems,
- (iv) One should be able to produce stable enzymes with sufficient kinetic activity and in bulk quantity at relatively low cost. Several enzymes are now commercially available and their prices are also decreasing.

Coenzyme immobilised anodes for BFC :

Many biological oxidation-reduction reactions utilise a coenzyme as a proton and electron carrier which functions in conjunction with a covalently linked enzyme specific for the substrate used as fuel. A typical example is glucose oxidase which uses flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) as a coenzyme in the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid. The

Fig. 1. The oxidation-reduction cycle of FAD which involves transfer of two protons and two electrons. Electrons are transferred to the electrode in step IV→I while the oxidised form is enzymatically reduced to FADH₂ (III) by the substrate which releases two protons and two electrons. The protons released in step III→IV are absorbed by the buffer and transported to cathode compartment.

complete redox cycle of this coenzyme is schematically represented in Fig. 1. The oxidation of fuel (SH_2) in presence of the enzyme (E) liberate two protons and two electrons. These can be taken up by the oxidised FAD (I) to give FADH₂ (III). Likewise, the regeneration of oxidised form of FAD involves sequential release of two protons (IV) and two electrons (I). In the fuel cell (Fig. 2), the two protons have to be transported from the anode compartment to the cathode. Protons being water soluble, they can easily pass into the aqueous phase from the coenzyme and then to the cathode compart-

ment. On the other hand, the two electrons have to be passed on to the electrode by a suitable mechanism. Our approach to circumvent this problem is based on immobilisation of FAD on graphite through semiconducting linkages such that an electron transport bridge can be established for a direct passage of electrons to the graphite anode. Such an electrode can then serve as a bioanode. In conjunction with an oxygen electrode, the biochemical fuel cell can yield voltages of 1 V or higher¹⁵.

Fig. 2. The conceptual drawing of a biochemical fuel cell based on FAD. The FAD immobilized on graphite is used as a cathode. Protons are transferred from the anodic to cathodic compartment giving rise to an internal proton current as opposed to electron current in the external circuit.

We have made systematic molecular orbital studies of the electron-flow diagrams of riboflavin during its redox cycle. The calculations show, as expected for aromatic ring systems, that the charge

distributions in all the four states of FAD are highly delocalised. However, in the electron release step IV→I the largest electron flux occurs from the two carbonyl groups. These then should serve as ideal sites for immobilising flavin on graphite through semiconducting linkages. The chemical steps involved in this process involves creating active centres on the graphite surface which can then be condensed with FAD to form covalent linkages between the electrode and the coenzyme. Cyclic voltamograms of the modified electrode show that FAD is active and undergoes the expected redox cycles. Further work on the design of BFC based on this approach is in progress.

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